

FIERCE

*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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1. INTRODUCTION :

FIERCE aims to revitalize the alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers at the national and transnational level in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and rising anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizations. FIERCE research and actions are grounded in intersectional feminist theory and practice that support democratic participation and innovation. Intersectional and cross-movement connections and alliances are FIERCE central staples; these are encouraged and supported through co-participatory processes and initiatives that the FIERCE community pursues with feminist movements and activists in different national contexts and transnationally.

1.1.1. How do we approach the question of Democratic Innovation in this report?

Within the FIERCE project a specific work has been done in defining democratic innovation, notably within the transversal analysis of the research results (WP3). This report draws conceptually on the literature review and analytical groundwork developed within the FIERCE project's Deliverable "D4.1 – Co-creation methodology and dialogue sessions reports" (FIERCE Project, 2024¹). A simplified overview of the state of the art of the research on democratic innovation is provided below to explain and clarify the choice of this report to focus on what the feminist actors self-define as democratic innovations.

Democratic innovation tends to be understood as forms of innovation within the context of representative democratic processes, notably in terms of governance within the institutions. Forms of innovation encompass for instance methodologies such as co-creation, citizens' panels and deliberations, participatory budgeting, which may lead to increased political participation. These innovations may come within the political governance structures (Bächtiger et al. 2018²; Elstub and Escobar 2019³) or build on an agonistic approach (Dean, 2017)⁴, which recognizes consideration to both informal and institutionalised forms of opposition, in which citizens can play an agonistic and oppositional role to institutions, as counterpowers (Rosanvallon 2006)⁵. These democratic innovations are expected to bring in an extension of public space.

Feminist critiques of the universalist mainstream conception of the public sphere (notably as developed by Habermas), such as that of Nancy Fraser, proposing to build 'feminist subaltern counterpublics', brought new ways of thinking about democracy and democratic processes. In Fraser's work, 'counterpublics' are conceived as parallel discursive arenas where members of subordinated social groups invent and circulate counterdiscourses, which in turn permits them to formulate oppositional interpretations of their identities, interests, and needs. These counterpublics may express themselves at the margins of the mainstream citizens' movements, and are therefore often

¹ D4.1 – Co-creation methodology and dialogue sessions reports is accessible here: <https://fierce-project.eu/public-deliverables/>

² Bächtiger, A., Dryzek, J. S., Mansbridge, J., & Warren, M. E. (Eds.). (2018). *The Oxford handbook of deliberative democracy*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198747369.001.0001>

³ Elstub, S., & Escobar, O. (2019). *Deliberative democracy: Issues and cases*. Edinburgh University Press.

⁴ Dean, J. (2017). *Doing politics: Radical praxis for a digital age*. Zed Books.

⁵ Rosanvallon, P. (2006). *Counter-democracy: Politics in an age of distrust* (A. Goldhammer, Trans.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511804031>

overseen. Feminist movements in current democracy may in large parts be considered as ‘subaltern counterpublics’.

Additionally, in recent years new forms of civic participation have emerged, notably via the rise of informal civil society, which can become an effective booster to European democracy, as highlighted by a 2022 research study by the [European Democracy Hub](#). These informal civic society spaces contribute to democratic health by providing space for flexible, productive, engaged and multiformat activism that professionalised NGOs struggle to provide. This research points to the necessity to look at how smaller, and sometimes informal, feminist groups develop their actions and consider their input into formal democratic processes but also into what can be called “everyday” democracy (i.e. actions in communities or at local level that aim, in the long run, to bring structural changes at a larger scale and prepare people for other forms of engaged citizenship).

FIERCE builds on such an understanding of democratic innovations, also apparent in the social movement literature. It highlights forms of innovations in governance and consensus making that go beyond those experimented within or with the institutions. It also pins down innovation linked to intersectional approaches and alliances, which often take the form of “counterpublics”.

Therefore, the project, with the FIERCE Actions, decided to analyse the shapes and forms of democratic innovation at a small scale, within the feminist movement, and during the implementation of projects conceived as forms of “democratic innovation” by the feminist activists and organisations themselves.

FIERCE has developed an understanding of democratic innovation based on feminist theory. Democracy is understood not only in terms of formal institutional democratic processes, but also in actions that stimulate and foster forms of active citizenship and beyond that actions that contribute to a renewal of the framing of issues in the public debate, notably by allowing the contribution and alliances of underrepresented groups and stakeholders and of experiential knowledge in this framing. Innovation, linked to the element of novelty, may appear in very different ways. Within the feminist movements it appears to take place in various dimensions of actions: in terms of governance within the movements and among the movements, in terms of the feminist approach to the understanding of an issue, in terms of the form that an action takes and/or in terms of its outputs. This understanding is presented in the following paragraphs in more details.

As part of the participatory action-research methodology, FIERCE supported the implementation of 18 FIERCE Actions. FIERCE Actions took various forms and shape, such as: campaign initiatives that counteract anti-gender speech, or that defend gender-related rights; ground actions that develop new ways of involving underrepresented groups in politics (such as street, artistic, and cultural activities); citizen reviews of participative democracy processes put in place at local and national levels and applying an intersectional feminist approach to participation; targeted feminist assemblies, speech groups, and encounters employing feminist practices, dedicated to defining solutions to barriers that impede democratic participation.

The FIERCE Actions have emerged from two different processes. First, some actions were proposed as the result of collaborative work elaborated within the FIERCE National Labs, groups of feminist organisations that have worked together on the topics of FIERCE almost since the beginning of the project. In each country, local and national feminist NGOs, collectives, and groups have gathered 3 times or more in the framework of a National Lab, coordinated by the FIERCE Partner in their country. These National Labs were part of the Research-Action methodology of FIERCE. Some of these labs have proposed and developed FIERCE Actions, and 7 FIERCE Actions emerged from the National Labs.

FIERCE wanted to be open to the possibility to develop FIERCE actions to a larger scope of organisations, therefore, it also published an Open Call. 11 FIERCE Actions were selected as a result of the open call. The selection process is described in more details in section I of this report.

"This report presents an analysis of how feminist movements define 'democratic innovation' from the bottom-up, following the implementation of the FIERCE Actions. It contributes to refining the conceptualisation of democratic innovation as developed within FIERCE. The analysis draws on responses to the questionnaire provided both by external feminist movements and by project partners involved in implementing Lab-derived actions. While both sources offer valuable insights, a distinction is made between bottom-up democratic innovations emerging autonomously from movements and those shaped through the institutional framework of the Labs. This report complements the state-of-the-art review conducted in WP3 and the analysis of democratic innovation within the previous functioning of the FIERCE Labs (Tasks 4.1 and 4.2).

Task 4.4: FIERCE actions: Testing democratic innovation actions in partnership with local and national feminist movements was led by European Alternatives, its team is therefore the primary writer of the report.

The primary source of information used in this report are:

- The presentations of the FIERCE actions by their main carriers, as presented in their response to the open call or registration (in the pre-action questionnaire). This questionnaire was elaborated by European Alternatives and reviewed by FIERCE project partners (See annex 1).
- The knowledge acquired by the team following the FIERCE action during the development of the actions, may it be during an introduction call online or within further communication during the course of implementation of the action, as well as the documentation of the actions shared with FIERCE by the main action carriers. The researchers also took part in the actions in their countries as observers.
- The responses to the post-action questionnaire: FIERCE action carriers answered to a questionnaire, in which the questions had been focussed on the various possible dimensions of democratic innovation identified within FIERCE. The questionnaire was elaborated by European Alternatives and reviewed by FIERCE consortium members, notably the scientific team in charge of the project from Aalborg University and ViLabs as project coordinator (see annex 2).

In summary, the data includes application documents and reporting by the FIERCE Action leaders. To this is added qualitative assessment from FIERCE partners. Representatives of FIERCE Partners took part in most of the FIERCE actions in person and therefore bring in external qualitative input in the analysis of the actions. The data has been analysed qualitatively by answer and by organisation.

It is important to note that 1/3 of the FIERCE actions (7 actions out of 18) have been coordinated by the project partners of FIERCE. The analysis therefore relies on both the views of the NGOs and collectives that have led FIERCE Actions and on the input developed by FIERCE partners.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE FIERCE ACTIONS

2.1.1. What Are FIERCE Actions?

FIERCE Actions are feminist-driven initiatives designed to promote democratic participation and innovation from an intersectional feminist perspective.

There were two ways in developing and choosing FIERCE Actions

- 7 actions were proposed as the result of collaborative work elaborated within the FIERCE National Labs, i.e. groups of feminist organisations that have worked together on the topics of FIERCE almost since the beginning of the project. In each country, local and national feminist NGOs, collectives, and groups have gathered 3 times or more in the frame of a National Lab, coordinated by the FIERCE Partner in their country. These National Labs were part of the Research-Action methodology of FIERCE. As defined in Deliverable D4.1, these Labs were conceived as hybrid, action-oriented spaces of dialogue aimed at generating concrete, politically relevant outcomes. While submitting an action proposal to the FIERCE Action call was not initially mandatory, many Labs chose to co-develop such proposals in response to urgent local or national issues identified through their collective work. Groups—comprising at least two participating organisations—were thus offered the opportunity to submit a FIERCE Action through a dedicated form, similar to the one used in the open call. The selection process was simplified since the FIERCE Partners in each country, who had coordinated and accompanied the development of the National Labs, were in charge of registering and following the FIERCE Action.
- 11 Actions were selected as the result of an open call. FIERCE issued and [open call](#) for the co-creation of FIERCE Actions, advertised between 31 July 2025 and 15 September 2025. The FIERCE Actions were expected to be political, cultural and/or artistic projects related to FIERCE's 5 intervention themes (Labour Market, Health and Reproductive Rights, LGBTQIA+ Rights, Migration, Gender-Based Violence) and to happen in one of the eight countries of the project (Greece, Denmark, Italy, Spain, France, Poland, Slovenia, Turkey). The call was geared towards actions that:
 - Counteract anti-gender speech and defend gender-related rights.
 - Involve underrepresented groups in politics through street, artistic, or cultural activities.
 - Review participative democracy processes at local and national levels.
 - Organize feminist assemblies, speech groups, and encounters to address barriers to democratic participation.

The selection criteria were the following: Objectives of the Action; Implementation; Democratic innovation; Feminist approach; and Expected outcomes.

61 applications were submitted as a result to the open call. The evaluation committee was composed of project partners and the Advisory Board Members. The selection took place at the end of September 2024. The FIERCE Actions took place between November 2024 and March 2025. Representatives of the FIERCE Actions were invited to join the community of learning from FIERCE, made of representatives of the partner organisations and of feminist organisations from the eight countries of the project and from European feminist organisations such as WIDE +, Gender 5+, IGLYO, Roma Rights Centre, at the start of their collaboration with FIERCE, within the [FIERCE Week](#), which

took place in Venice in early November 2025. The budget allocated to each FIERCE Action, including the participation to FIERCE Week was limited to a maximum of 4500 euros per action, sometimes less depending on the scale of the project, the budget requested, and/or the availability of funding.

The selected FIERCE Actions range from public campaigns against gender-based violence, to feminist housing projects, to the organisation of theatre workshops to boost participation of migrants, the production of comic strips or board games against LGBTphobia and cultural events mixing diverse forms of interventions from classic round table discussions to workshops, exhibition, artistic performances and community kitchen.

2.1.2. Who has been involved in developing FIERCE Actions?

There are several types of organisations involved in leading the FIERCE actions. Here is a quick presentation of the groups of people this report is referring to:

FIERCE project Partners: there are 11 partner organisations in the [FIERCE research consortium](#) from 8 countries: 7 Universities, 2 NGOs, and 2 SMEs. In each country of the project, the FIERCE Partners have been coordinating National Labs. Most FIERCE partners have a team dedicated to leading the research for the FIERCE project.

FIERCE Action main carriers: By “carriers” is meant the collective or organisation that has mainly carried out the implementation of the FIERCE Action. It does not imply any hierarchy. The type of organisations leading the FIERCE Action fall in two categories:

- Organisations which applied to the open call: this includes NGOs, collectives, associations, and artists’ groups whose actions have been selected via an open call.
- Networks of feminist organisations issued from the National Labs: all or some members of the National Labs have proposed actions linked to the work conducted in their labs. The administrative and financial coordination has been provided by each FIERCE Partner in their country, while the implementation of the action was delivered collectively.

2.1.3. List of FIERCE Actions

Below is a complete list of the 18 FIERCE Actions.

Country:	Organization name:	Main thematic	Title:	Summary:
Denmark	Everyday Sexism Project Denmark (National lab)	Fighting discrimination and sexism in marginalized groups	Intersectional Bystander Workshop and Game at the Youth Democracy Festival 2024	Creation of a Dialogue card-game and Workshop combatting intersectional sexism where young people (last year of elementary school and high school), where they learn how to become an active bystander to fight discrimination and sexism of marginalized groups. The workshop focused on different scenarios, with intersectional experiences of discrimination.
Denmark	Center for Violence Prevention	GBV	Orange days in Aalborg	Events, including public stage (theatre) happenings, talks with organisations, distribution of informational goodie bags, and art exhibition. It included Support Groups and Workshops
France	Tant que je serai noire	Black women political representation and rights	Savoir Pouvoir: Réapproprions nos droits démocratiques	Empowering initiative designed to help Black women and gender minorities understand their democratic rights in France. Popular education model: workshops, interactive seminars, and accessible resources. Cultivate community leaders: Build a network of leaders who advocate for their communities and mobilize others to participate in democratic processes.
France	coordinated by European Alternatives (National Lab)	Fighting Anti-Gender Mobilisations	Online Resources on How to fight Anti-Gender	A platform gathering documents and tools produced by feminists NGOs on how to fight anti-gender and a feminist public event on fighting anti-gender
Greece	The boat collective	Migration	Musafir	3 days Workshop on re-memory, bodies, borders, to conceive a theatre play with migrants
Greece	Aristotle University (National Lab)	GBV, Fighting Anti-Gender	FIERCE	Series of roundtables in Karditsa, Volos, Rethymno, bringing together researchers, activists, and feminist associations to share research findings on anti-gender movements. The themes included: legislative backlash and anti-sexist movements, feminist networks and the fight against gender-based violence, and the emergence of LGBTQI+ movements. Based on a collaborative and horizontal methodology, these meetings fostered critical exchanges, enriching research with local experiences and strengthening the connections between activism and feminist knowledge production.
Italy	Smart Venice s.r.l. (National Lab)	Education to Difference (schools and highschools)	Self-defence manual for teachers working in education to differences	Self-manual for teachers in schools, providing a set of practical strategies to improve their response capacity when facing the obstacles and situations of violence, notably anti-gender discourse, in their day-to-day activities.
Italy	Tourbillon ETS	GBV, Housing, Care	Arti femministe a Santa Chiara. Trasformare, sentire, formarsi	Role-play simulation on gender violence, Presentation of a self-organized community housing project, promoting sustainable, feminist urban spaces. Feminist kitchen, exploring care work and its intersections with gender, race, and labor conditions. The final objective is to realise a network of feminist practices to promote meetings and building of a feminist community that work on thinking of alternative ways of doing politics.
Poland	University of Gdańsk (National Lab)	Labour Rights	Women's labour rights	Campaign women's labour rights' provided information on the gender-specific labour rights and the ways to secure them. Apart from the information strictly connected to the labor code, the action will also include information on and the ways how to combat more 'soft' forms of gender-based discrimination at the workplace.
Poland	Fundacja Kocham Dębniaki	GBV LBTQI+ rights Migration	gender debunking guerilla	Campaign - The campaign utilized stickers with QR codes, strategically placed in public spaces across Warsaw and Krakow, providing a simple and accessible way for people to obtain comprehensive knowledge about gender-related issues.
Poland	Fundacja Widzialne	Abortion	Akcja Aborcja	The action promoted access to safe abortion within the provincial and rural areas of Pomeranian region in cooperation with the Polish organization Abortion Dream Team, specifically via workshops on reproductive rights.
Slovenia	Mirovni Institut (National Lab)	Reproductive rights	Reproductive rights: On health, sexuality and equality of	The feminist exhibition presents the key milestones in the history of reproductive rights in Slovenia regarding: contraception, abortion, sexual education, artificial insemination and parenting rights, and violence in reproductive health. The exhibition was intended as a public intervention to reach a broader audience.
Slovenia	Transfeminist Initiative TransAkcija	LGBTQI and Trans-rights	LGBTIQ+ Radar	The action provided effective Response to Anti-Gender Narratives: Address and counter incidents of anti-LGBTIQ+ hate, such as discriminatory laws, media attacks, and violence at public events. Data collection on aggressions (in the media and physical aggressions) against LGBTQI+. It has created a Shared Database and Collaborative Platform, and created opportunities to raise public awareness and to build support. It contributed to solidify ing the newly formed consortium of LGBTQI+ organizations and activists.
Spain	Mujeres Supervivientes	Fight Anti-Gender movements	Feminist Day; Theory and action in the face of Antifeminism	Round Table & Campaign on antifeminism in Spain
Spain	Parcela de Tierra	Intersectionality and Decoloniality	La Cenicera	Brasas project was a public event aiming at creating links between intersectional feminist, decolonial and queer organisations, as well as migrant and artistic organisations, in order to promote gender equality and combat the extreme right-wing discourse in Spain in the public space. It proposed a round table, a dinner and an artistic and cultural event, open to the different collectives and the general public.
Turkey	Koç University (National Lab)	Feminism and Democracy	Feminist co-creation: strengthening voice and increasing visibility	Production of a policy brief reviews existing participatory democracy processes utilizing an activist lens in combination with scholarly knowledge. It includes the production of a mini-documentary that captured activists' ideas about the current state of democracy and the feminist movement and their imaginations about the future of both. It serves as a visual tool for broader outreach and awareness-raising.
Turkey	Women Worker Solidarity Association	Women Workers	Internal training and forum	Internal training for Kadınışçi reporters and volunteers on feminist methods and politics; Forum on the possibilities of feminist solidarity with workers' resistance.
Turkey	Kuir-Trans Feminist Karikatür Okulu	LBTQI+	Özgür Renkler LGBTQI+ Demeği	A Queer-Trans Feminist Cartoon school was organised for 2 days. The workshops were organised in collaboration with queer-trans feminist illustrators, allowing LGBTQI+'s to express their stories, experiences and social struggles in an artistic way.

All FIERCE Actions are presented in detail on the FIERCE Website in [a dedicated section](#).

2.1.4. Where did the FIERCE Actions take place?

The 18 FIERCE Actions took place in the 8 countries of the FIERCE project: Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Slovenia, Spain, Poland and Turkey. In Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Slovenia and Spain, there were 2 FIERCE Actions in Each country. The FIERCE Partners decided to support 3 FIERCE Actions in Poland and Turkey, based on the national context in terms of gender rights, the costs of the actions and the quality of the actions in the local context.

In the selection process, specific attention was given to covering non-urban areas and less privileged regions, when possible, as well as urban areas. Several actions also took place online, therefore having a reach within a whole language area.

1. Greece: Karditsa, Volos, Rethymno, Athens. Language used: Greek
2. Spain: Seville, Valencia, Language used: Spanish
3. Turkey: Istanbul, Bursa, Language used: Turkish
4. Denmark: Aalborg, Copenhagen. Language used: Danish
5. France: Paris and online. Language used: French
6. Italy: Naples, online and print. Language used: Italian
7. Poland: Warsaw, Krakow, Sopot, Sztum. Languages used: Polish and Ukrainian
8. Slovenia: Ljubljana and online, Languages used: Slovenian and English
9. Online Actions and Campaigns and prints, notably in Slovenian, Ukrainian, Polish, Italian and French

Below is a visualisation of where the FIERCE Actions took place:

Acting beyond main urban centres is key. For instance, decentralising feminist discourse and building bridges among communities in the periphery was a key objective of the Greek actions in smaller cities. It was a way to decentralise discourse by shifting attention to the periphery, i.e. areas often neglected in academic research and political discourse. This provided spaces for local feminist groups to

exchange their experiences, insights, and challenges. Moving between different cities enabled the transfer of ideas and strategies from one community to another, reinforcing the collaborative framework between participants. This process revealed local challenges and policy gaps related to gender violence and oppression, while also creating safe spaces for dialogue and the sharing of personal narratives. By effectively connecting public discourse with lived experiences, these efforts not only strengthened bonds among participants but also laid the groundwork for sustained collaboration beyond the project's timeline.

2.1.5. What were the FIERCE Actions mostly about?

The main topics tackled by the FIERCE Actions were gender-based violence and fighting anti-gender movements. These reflect the terms of the open call and of the FIERCE Project. Gender-based violence also appears in the FIERCE research as the main thematic on which feminist movements of the last 10 years have been focussing throughout Europe. In the course of the selection of FIERCE Actions, the selection committee tried to get as diverse a set of actions overall as possible, so that they complement each other thematically and cover a wide spectrum of issues.

Most FIERCE Actions dealt with more than one thematic. The graph below represents all of the main topics tackled. Therefore, more than 18 thematics appear.

2.1.6. What were the main forms of actions of the FIERCE Actions?

Most FIERCE Actions combined several forms of actions, notably when it comes to public events that combined round tables, cultural events, workshops and/or exhibitions.

- The most used form of action was that of cultural events or activity, which were used in 7 of the FIERCE Actions
- There were 2 exhibitions: 1 on Reproductive Rights in Slovenia, 1 on surviving sexual violence in Denmark.
- 2 FIERCE actions focussed solely on workshops, notably some actions focussed on internal workshops within a given group or community, as a basis for self-empowerment and learning in a safe environment
- One film was produced, together with a policy brief as campaign support and material
- Cartoons were produced as a way to raise awareness and to support self-consciousness within the LGBTQIA+ community
- One self-defence manual

The graph below presents the main forms the FIERCE Actions took. As several actions developed more than one type of actions, there are more than 18 types of actions presented.

2.1.7. Outputs from the FIERCE Actions:

FIERCE Actions were designed to support feminist initiatives addressing local and national priorities, without requiring predefined deliverables. While not all actions led to publicly disseminated materials, most generated meaningful outcomes—such as capacity-building, political mobilisation, or strengthened networks. In some cases, these outcomes also took the form of concrete and shareable outputs, including training sessions, reports, or advocacy tools. The most notable of these are listed below:

- 1 set of cartoons on LGBTQIA+ rights in Turkey
- 1 set of dialogue cards games on fighting sexism from Denmark
- 1 set of exhibition panels produced in Slovenian and English and [available online](#)
- 1 film in Turkish and one policy brief in Turkish and English
- 1 [online platform](#) on fighting anti-gender in French

- 1 database and online platform about LGBTQI+ rights in Slovenian
- 1 manual for teachers on facing violence notably when teaching about sexual and reproductive rights in Italian.
- 1 Booklet about abortion in Polish
- Campaign stickers on rights of women in Polish and Ukrainian
-

Below are some examples of the outputs of the FIERCE Actions:

1. Cover of the manual of self-defense for teachers (Italy)

2. Sticker in Ukrainian, Gender Debunking Guerilla, Warsaw, Krakow. Saying "for sexual intercourse, what's necessary? (a) consent? (b) consent? (c) consent ?

3. Booklet about Abortion distributed by Widzialne Foundation - So far, 150 copies have been distributed, and plans are underway to translate it into Ukrainian and English

2. Poster from the street exhibition on reproductive rights, Slovenia

5. Cartoon on LGBTQI+ Rights in Turkey

"Gayler gay barlar nedeniyle çoğaldı!" / "Gays have increased in number due to gay bars!"

"İyi de abla, burada gay bar yok!" / "But sister, there is no gay bar here!"

3. ANALYSIS OF THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE FIERCE ACTIONS TO DEMOCRATIC INNOVATION

Democratic innovation is not limited to modernising institutions or broadening citizen participation. At a small-scale, feminist movements implement and experiment with new **modes of governance, forms of mobilisation and frameworks for political action**, in order to make democracy more inclusive and genuinely participatory.

FIERCE Actions demonstrate that intersectional feminist struggles are not just sectoral demands, but **levers for democratic transformation**. By challenging power relations and integrating the experiences of marginalised groups into the design and implementation of political actions, they play an active part in renewing democratic practices.

The responses to the questionnaire identified three major aspects of this contribution:

- **Transformation of forms of governance:** FIERCE Actions are experimenting with horizontal and participative decision-making models, which enable an effective redistribution of power and recognition of the expertise resulting from real-life experiences.
- **Redefining modes of intervention:** these initiatives are developing approaches rooted in social justice, popular education and the production of situated knowledge, aimed at rebuilding democracy based on the needs and demands of historically excluded groups.
- **Innovation in forms of mobilisation and action:** By incorporating creative and digital tools - such as activism, the use of digital and interactive technologies, or performative modes of action - these initiatives are renewing forms of political engagement and awareness-raising, thereby broadening the democratic spaces and audiences mobilised (II.C.).

Democratic innovation, as promoted by FIERCE Actions, is not just a matter of including new stakeholders in existing structures, but of rethinking these structures themselves.

In this section, we will first analyse how FIERCE Actions are redefining governance and democratic participation (II.A.), before examining their feminist intervention logics and their impact on democratic practices (II.B.), and then the forms of action and mobilisation they are experimenting with to transform public space and modes of engagement (II.C.).

3.1.1. Governance

The governance of a project or initiative refers to all the decision-making, steering and collective management mechanisms that govern its operation. It is determined by who makes the decisions, how they are adopted and how the stakeholders are involved.

FIERCE Actions **question traditional governance frameworks** and **redefine decision-making processes**. For them, the inclusion of minority or marginalised groups and the adoption of intersectional governance are not only **ethical imperatives**, but also **fundamental levers for renewing democratic practices**.

Democratic governance means more than simply consulting the players involved; it also means effectively redistributing power and structuring the project in such a way that everyone has a say in its strategic direction.

FIERCE Actions innovate by developing **inclusive modes of governance** that integrate a diversity of stakeholders traditionally under-represented in decision-making bodies. This diversity may be understood in different ways:

- **Community-based:** racialised women, migrants, LGBTQAI+, precarious workers, survivors of violence.
- **Intergenerational:** collaboration between young and experienced activists.
- **Socioprofessional:** activists, researchers, artists, social workers, politicians and institutions.
- **Statutory:** participation of volunteers, salaried employees, members of political councils and informal activists.
- **Geographically diverse:** Several FIERCE Actions have focused on reaching people who are geographically distant from services and information.

This inclusion is essential for renewing democratic practices, by ensuring that **decisions are co-constructed with those directly affected by structural inequalities.**

Involving a diversity of stakeholders involved or developing multi-stakeholder partnerships

Representative democracy functioning on the basis of voting is in crisis. New forms of involvement with democracy are to be developed to make sure that all have their say in the way the decisions are made.

The FIERCE Actions leaders recognize that **allowing participation** of marginalised communities, even outside of what is recognised as official political decision making processes, constitutes a path of active citizenship and is part of fully functioning democratic societies. It applies the concept of **everyday democracy**, which relies on the idea that communities that create and sustain equitable and inclusive public dialogue can form the cornerstone of a vibrant democracy, may it be at local, national or transnational level.

The FIERCE Actions consider effective representation of groups that have historically been excluded from spaces of power as a key element of democratic innovation. It is not just a question of a symbolic presence on consultative bodies, but **of a far-reaching transformation of the dynamics of power** and recognition of the expertise that comes from real-life experience.

Some FIERCE Action focused on involving diverse and underrepresented groups within their action: The feminist organisations involved in these actions are calling for an approach in which the participation of racialised women, precarious workers, migrant women, survivors of violence and LGBTQIA+ people is not peripheral, but becomes central to the decision-making processes.

- **The "Savoir Pouvoir⁶" action of *Tant que je serai noire*⁷ (France):** This initiative has developed political education training for black women and gender minorities, with content designed and piloted directly by the main people concerned. The project grew out of a need expressed during post-legislative election discussion circles in 2024, demonstrating that the communities concerned must be **actors rather than spectators in democratic processes**. It **also enables knowledge to be returned to the people concerned, promoting their political empowerment.**
- **The Center for Violence Prevention's Orange Days in Aalborg project (Denmark):** By actively involving survivors of gender-based violence as well as organisations representing minorities

⁶ Knowing – Being able to” (translation by authors)

⁷ As long as I will be Black (translation by authors)

(LGBT+ Danmark, Reden, DareGender), this action demonstrated that the diversity of experiential knowledge is essential for rethinking institutional responses. By combining these groups, the action amplified under-represented voices and strengthened cross-community solidarity, illustrating how inclusion strengthens democratic innovation.

Multi-stakeholder partnerships were privileged by other FIERCE Actions, as a way **to cross-fertilise knowledge and expertise** between social movements, academia, politics and local institutions. These collaborations make it possible to combine activist and scientific knowledge to formulate appropriate responses to contemporary democratic challenges. They also contribute to legitimising intersectional feminist struggles in the public and institutional arena.

- **"Women's labour rights" project by Kadın İşçi (Turkey)**: Focusing on the struggles of women workers, particularly on issues of gender, class and exploitation at work, this initiative searched for ways of strengthening the links between feminist movements and trade union activism, by making visible the double oppression of women workers, both in the domestic sphere and in the world of work. By integrating gender issues into trade union struggles, the action is challenging masculinist bias and gendered hierarchies in the Turkish trade union world, which often focuses on general demands without always taking into account the specificities linked to gender inequalities. This project aimed at making labor struggles more inclusive and strengthening the democratic participation of women workers in areas where they are sometimes marginalised.
- **The Radar LGBTIQ+ project by Inicijativa TransAkcija (Slovenia)** brought together feminist and LGBTIQ+ associations in an intersectional consortium, where different areas of expertise (activist, legal, media) come together to structure a collective response to hate speech. Rather than relying solely on institutions or decisions taken in high places, this approach shows how activists self-organise to better defend the rights of minorities, using a more horizontal and collaborative form of alternative governance.

Horizontal structures and participatory practices

One of the major contributions of the **FIERCE Actions** lies in the experimentation with **horizontal models of governance**, which break with traditional hierarchical logics. Rather than imposing decisions, more than half of these initiatives have favoured **systems in which negotiation, consensus and the active participation of communities play a central role**.

These practices take the form of:

- **A fair distribution of power** between employees, volunteers and community members.
- **Open and collective decision-making processes**, avoiding the concentration of power among a few individuals.
- **Adaptive governance**, which takes into account the realities experienced by participants and adjusts according to their needs.
- Co-creation has been important in the approach to FIERCE Action development and implementation. It was notably adopted in several of the FIERCE actions stemming from the national labs, which worked explicitly on collaborative ways to organize deliberation and participation within the networks. For instance, the Greek FIERCE actions developed by the National Lab **consolidated a Feminist Methodology for Working in Groups with Non-Hierarchical Structures**. It employed a methodology developed by the Greek team during the

National Labs, a framework designed to promote horizontal collaboration and open exchanges without imposing rigid moderation. Knowledge-building was approached as a relational process, emerging through transparent dialogue with our interlocutors. The individuals involved in the FIERCE actions had previously participated in earlier stages of the research, particularly the National Labs and interviews. Revisiting these collaborations and sharing findings were integral to the commitment to reciprocity, transparency, and collaborative knowledge-building. This approach aligned with the feminist research methodology, which prioritises transparency, continuous collaboration, and consent while consolidating findings through the participants' activist and research practices.

By including minority groups in decision-making processes and promoting horizontal structures, these initiatives are helping to build more inclusive practices, where power is redistributed and shared collectively.

In addition to their participatory governance, FIERCE Actions are distinguished by their **intervention logic** and **feminist approach**. By incorporating the principles of intersectional feminism, they build spaces for emancipation where speaking out, producing knowledge and taking collective action become levers for social change.

3.1.2. Intervention logic and feminist approach of FIERCE Actions

In the context of this project, the **logics of intervention** refer to the strategies put in place by organisations to reach their audiences and objectives. More specifically, the aim is to analyse **how these organisations design and implement their interventions**, the practices they mobilise and how these practices contribute to renewing democratic frameworks.

Far from confining themselves to sectoral demands or top-down approaches, these initiatives have favoured **mobilisation based on the experiences and needs of the communities** concerned. The methodology adopted was based on a number of structuring principles, which were consistently integrated into their actions:

Community-based and bottom-up intervention

FIERCE Actions have mostly chosen a bottom-up approach, based on self-organisation and empowerment of marginalised groups. Rather than imposing solutions, they have left it up to the communities concerned to define their priorities and methods of action.

- **The project "Arti femministe a Santa Chiara. Trasformare, sentire, formarsi" by Tourbillon ETS (Italy)** developed bottom-up intervention. The action **developed trans-feminist pedagogies**, based on collective and critical forms of learning (role-playing, public interventions, mutual support). It **created spaces for emancipation**, where the experiences of women and gender minorities become **tools for democratic transformation**. It **challenged dominant norms**, by questioning the way in which political and social systems perpetuate the marginalisation of subaltern groups.
- **Boat Collectiv and Musafir's 'Survive the Borderlands' project (Greece)** has developed a **feminist abolitionist approach to borders**, inspired by the work of **Saidiya Hartman and Toni Morrison** on the memory and history of oppression. The organisation states: *"We use feminist/queer and anti-racist practices to tell the stories that could not be told within the existing social and political context"*. By integrating narrative and performative tools, this action has enabled migrant communities to reclaim their collective memory and reconstruct spaces

for political expression over invisibilised narratives, in opposition to institutional policies of exclusion.

An intersectional feminist approach

Inspired by the work of Kimberlé Crenshaw and Patricia Hill Collins, a large majority of the FIERCE Actions have integrated the analysis of intersecting oppressions into the development of their strategies. By recognising the interlocking forms of domination - whether linked to gender, class, ethnicity or sexual orientation - these initiatives have worked to make visible the exclusions produced by traditional democratic structures.

- **The "LGBTIQ+ Radar" project, *iniciativa TransAkcija (Slovenia)***, stated that its work was *"deeply rooted in intersectional feminism, which recognises that different forms of oppression, such as sexism, homophobia, transphobia and racism, are interconnected and cannot be dealt with in isolation"*, and thus to propose responses adapted to the cumulative experiences of marginalised groups.
- **The women's labour rights project by *Kadın İşçi (Turkey)*** articulated a denunciation of the intertwining of patriarchy and capitalism, stating that *"patriarchy and capitalism are hierarchical systems that intertwine and reinforce each other and that patriarchal capitalism is a structure that oppresses women and exploits their labour in the workplace, at home and in trade unions. Feminism is defined as a form of struggle against patriarchal capitalism in the private and public spheres."* In its action, the organisation also highlighted the way in which *"not only capital, but also men exploit women's work"* and insisted on the need to *"make visible the specific forms of exploitation suffered by women workers, both in the domestic sphere and in workplaces and trade unions"*.
- **In the "Jornada Feminista: Teoría Y Acción Frente Al Antifeminismo" project by *Mujeres Supervivientes* and the *Brasas de Parcela de Tierra* project (Spain)**, the organisations have based their actions on a decolonial reading of feminism, deconstructing colonial legacies and subverting white cultural hegemony through collective artistic and political practices. Several other FIERCE Actions have linked their intersectional approach to an **anti-racist and decolonial reading of feminism**.

Popular education and the production of situated knowledge

Some FIERCE Actions have focused on **enhancing the value of knowledge** and on **transforming the spaces in which it is transmitted** by promoting popular education schemes, which have established themselves as tools for emancipation and political transformation. By encouraging the production of knowledge rooted in community experience, they have helped to reinvest the public arena with alternative narratives and critical practices.

- **The LGBTIQ+ radar project (Slovenia):** *"Our action challenges heteronormative norms and argues for a feminism that embraces all gender identities"*. The organisation has developed an intersectional and queer feminist approach in which art is used as a tool to raise awareness and bring about political transformation. By giving LGBTIQ+ people the opportunity to recount their experiences through artistic productions, this action has made it possible to invest the public space with alternative narratives, thereby contributing to the democratic recognition of minorities.
- **The Savoir Pouvoir project (France)** asserted that *"the political education of black women and gender minorities must be designed by and for them"*. This action proposed a feminist popular

school enabling black women and gender minorities to appropriate political and media codes. This initiative illustrates how popular education can be a tool for emancipation and the reappropriation of democratic rights.

- **The Sexism from a Minority Perspective project (Denmark)**, which has developed an **educational card game**. One of the organizations that have taken part in this action, Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, explains that *"our action is based on an educational format designed for young people, integrating the principles of non-formal education and critical reflexivity"*. Inspired by **Paulo Freire**, the initiative enables participants to explore **the mechanisms of sexism and harassment through role-playing and group discussions**.

These initiatives show that democratic innovation also involves transforming the spaces for debate and the ways in which knowledge is accessed.

- In a similar approach, the **Kocham Debniki Foundation (Poland)** has used interactive tools (such as QR codes distributed in public spaces) to facilitate access to reliable information on gender-based violence and reproductive health. This innovative approach helped to bypass institutional barriers and reach a wider audience.

3.1.3. Innovation in forms of mobilisation and action

Transforming public space into democratic space: activism and performance art

One of the major contributions of FIERCE Actions lies in their ability to **reinvest public space as a place of democratic production**. These initiatives have experimented with modes of action based on visibility, questioning and the reappropriation of urban space. Far from being simply tools for raising awareness, these artistic and performative interventions **are reinventing the methods of democratic engagement** by incorporating participative, immersive and collective forms.

By mobilising art as a space for resistance, they are demonstrating that **democracy is not confined to formal institutions**, but is also played out in the street, in cultural practices and in the capacity of citizens to produce counter-narratives and inscribe their demands in the public space. These actions are particularly innovative in contexts where feminist and LGBTQI+ movements face strategies of invisibilisation and repression.

Feminist and queer activism as counter-narrative:

- The Queer-Trans Feminist Cartoon project by Özgür Renkler Derneği (Turkey) is a good illustration of this. In a Turkish context marked by a rise in anti-gender discourse and increased censorship of feminist and LGBTQI+ cultural productions, this initiative used comics as a political medium. By combining visual storytelling with militant engagement, it has produced alternative narratives denouncing the repression of gender minorities and challenging heteronormative norms. Far from simply raising awareness, this action strengthened the capacity of marginalised communities to produce their own representations, thereby renewing democratic practices by regaining control over the collective imagination.
- The Feminist Exhibition on Reproductive Rights organized by *Mirovni Institute and University of Ljubljana* (Slovenia): One of the innovative aspects of this initiative lies in its ability to transform **a static exhibition into a political challenge**. By setting up in unconventional public places (public transport, community spaces, universities), it redefined the democratic uses of urban

space, creating places for debate accessible to a variety of audiences. What's more, its interactive format enabled spectators to take ownership of the content and contribute to the production of knowledge, underlining a logic of participatory democracy and feminist popular education.

Public performances and interventions

The intersection between artistic performance and political mobilisation was experimented with through various actions, highlighting the role of the **body and emotion in the reappropriation of public space**. These performances, far from being mere stagings, generated **new spaces for political socialisation**, where uninitiated audiences were confronted with the realities of feminist and queer struggles.

- Musafir (Greece)
This initiative has developed a unique approach by mobilising theatre, visual arts and music to explore the bodily and collective memory of gendered borders and oppression. By considering the body as a space for the territorialisation of power, Musafir has experimented with a sensory pedagogy of resistance, in which art becomes a means of reappropriating the narratives obscured by dominant structures. This approach, inspired by decolonial feminist theories, has helped to renew mobilisation strategies by proposing a political commitment based on the embodiment and lived experience of discrimination.
- Orange Days in Aalborg by the Center for Voldsforebyggelse (Denmark): This initiative is part of a reflection on how immersive performances can raise political awareness more effectively than traditional campaigns. By recreating scenes of support for victims of gender-based violence in the public space, it confronted passers-by with the realities experienced by survivors. Making community support more visible strengthened understanding of the dynamics of feminist solidarity and restorative justice, introducing a more participatory and embodied approach to feminist struggles.

By experimenting with these new forms of mobilisation, FIERCE Actions are showing that **democracy is not limited to institutional representation but is also built on cultural practices and the use of public space**. They are reintroducing **the body and emotion into democratic engagement**, renewing the ways in which politics is challenged.

Digital and media spaces: mobilising, raising awareness and resisting

The rise of digital technology has profoundly changed the way people engage with politics, offering **new spaces for expression and mobilisation** for feminist and LGBTQI+ movements. However, these spaces are also places of conflict, where anti-feminist and anti-gender discourses proliferate, while the surveillance and censorship of activists is intensifying in several national contexts.

FIERCE Actions have used digital technology not only as **a tool for disseminating information and raising awareness**, but also as **an arena for resistance and political structuring**. By developing alternative platforms, digital campaigns and counter-discourse strategies, these initiatives have shown that **new technologies are not neutral** and can be used to **redefine democratic practices online**.

Digital campaigns and data-driven mobilisation

- The "gender debunking guerilla": QR codes and digital campaigns project by Fundacja Kocham Dębni (Poland): Against a backdrop of restrictions on access to abortion and reproductive health information, and the arrival of Ukrainian refugees, this initiative has developed an

innovative device by integrating QR codes into urban spaces. Placed in strategic locations (public toilets, bus stops, cafés), these QR codes redirect people to feminist resources on sexual and reproductive rights and contacts for access to sexual and reproductive health care. This approach bypasses institutional censorship by giving citizens anonymous and secure access to essential content, transforming the digital space into an extension of the fight for access to rights. This approach has also made it possible to reach audiences far removed from traditional activism, by facilitating individual and discreet appropriation of information.

- **LGBTQI Radar (Slovenia):** This initiative demonstrated how digital platforms can be used to ensure the continuity of feminist struggles in contexts of repression. By developing a secure space for organisation and discussion, this action has made it possible to structure a feminist counter-power online. Far from being a simple communication channel, this platform has experimented with self-management practices and the pooling of resources, constituting a laboratory for alternative democratic practices in the fight against disinformation.
- **French National Lab's Fight Anti-Gender Movement project:** This initiative has set up an online platform listing the main arguments of anti-gender movements, responses and tools developed within the feminist movements. Its innovation is based on the results of FIERCE research, developed using a participatory methodology, involving researchers, activists and journalists in the production and dissemination of verified and accessible content. This approach will not only strengthen the resilience of feminist movements in the face of disinformation campaigns. Combating misinformation requires in-depth documentation and an effective dissemination strategy. By analysing the rhetorical mechanisms of anti-gender discourse and training activists to deconstruct these narratives, it has encouraged the development of a **proactive feminism**, capable of structuring a well-argued and accessible response.

3.1.3.1. Feminist advocacy and lobbying: influencing the legislative and political framework

FIERCE Actions have also entered the legislative and decision-making arenas. In a number of national contexts, where public policies are regressing on the rights of women and gender minorities, these initiatives have demonstrated that **feminist advocacy is not just a matter of questioning public authorities**, but constitutes a **genuine strategy for political influence, rooted in forms of bottom-up and collective mobilisation**.

By combining **research, the production of knowledge and public campaigns**, these actions have helped to **renew forms of democratic commitment**, by demonstrating that **institutions are not fixed spaces, but can be transformed by feminist action**.

- **Campaign for equal pay by the National Lab in Poland (coordinated by *the University of Gdańsk*):** In a country where equal pay remains an underestimated issue in political debates, this initiative has adopted an innovative strategy by combining **grassroots mobilisation and institutional pressure**. Rather than limiting itself to an abstract demand, it has developed a **map of pay inequalities by sector**, based on workers' testimonies and economic data. This methodology made it possible to **materialise the pay gap and make it visible to decision-makers and public opinion**. By involving the trade unions in the campaign, this action also helped to **link feminist and social struggles**, thereby contributing to a renewal of the dynamics of collective commitment.
- **Policy brief and film in Turkey:** In a context marked by the repression of feminist and LGBTQI+ movements, this initiative demonstrated that **advocacy is not limited to drafting policy**

recommendations but can be a lever for transnational mobilisation. By combining a **policy document aimed at the European institutions** and a **film giving a voice to local activists**, this action combined **institutional strategy and activist storytelling**. This hybrid approach has helped **to raise the profile of Turkish feminisms on the European stage**, while providing an essential documentation tool for other movements in the struggle.

3.1.3.2. Raising awareness among decision-makers and transnational alliances

- *Roundtables and Networking by the National Lab in Greece:* In a context where anti-gender policies are gaining ground within European governments, this initiative demonstrated **the importance of spaces for dialogue between activists, researchers and politicians**. Unlike traditional advocacy formats, which are often vertical and focused on challenging institutions, these roundtables encouraged **a more collaborative approach**, enabling recommendations to be drawn up jointly by the players concerned. This method strengthened **the legitimacy of feminist demands**, by demonstrating that **public policies cannot be devised without the people primarily concerned**.

These initiatives illustrate that **feminist advocacy is not simply an institutional approach but is based on a transformation of the way in which public policies are developed**. By incorporating forms of expertise drawn from real-life experience, and by combining citizen mobilisation and legislative work, these initiatives help **strengthen the participatory dimension of democracy** and make feminist demands part of sustainable political dynamics.

3.1.3.3. Reclaiming living spaces: towards an embodied democracy

FIERCE Actions have shown that **democracy is not only played out in institutions or street mobilisations, but also in everyday spaces**. Faced with the dynamics of urban exclusion, precarious housing and structural inequalities affecting women and gender minorities, The project Feminism in Santa Chiara has sought to **reinvest domestic and collective space as a place for social and political transformation**.

This action is particularly innovative in a context in which **policies of privatisation and gentrification are reinforcing inequalities**, and where access to housing and community spaces has become a central issue for marginalised groups. By experimenting with alternative forms of housing, resource sharing and collective care, this project is **reinventing democracy based on practices of solidarity**.

Housing and the city as spaces of resistance and self-management

- *The "Arti femministe a Santa Chiara" project by Tourbillon ETS (Italy):* Faced with the rise in evictions and gentrification, which particularly affects insecure and LGBTQI+ women, this initiative has developed a collective housing model inspired by feminist and queer self-management practices. Far from being a simple response to the housing crisis, this project has experimented with **a new form of local democracy**, where decisions are taken collectively and traditional power relationships are deconstructed. As one participant puts it, **"living together also means fighting isolation and rebuilding forms of daily resistance"**. By claiming housing as a right and not as a commodity, this action proposes a **political reappropriation of domestic space**.

Feminist cuisine as a space for politicisation

- *The "Arti femministe a Santa Chiara" project by Tourbillon ETS (Italy) has also developed a feminist cuisine.* By setting up spaces where women, particularly migrants and those in

precarious situations, can cook collectively and share their experiences, this initiative has turned food into **an arena for combating gender and class inequalities**. The project has helped to **raise the profile and value of care work**, while creating cross-cutting solidarity between different communities. One of the organisers explained that "**reclaiming the kitchen also means asserting our place in the public arena and in the local economy**", underlining the political significance of this action.

By placing **housing, cooking and mutual aid at the heart of feminist struggles**, these initiatives demonstrate that **democracy is not limited to institutional spaces but is also built through collective practices that redefine ways of living and social organisation**.

Self-defence and the well-being of activists: strengthening collective empowerment

In a context where feminist and LGBTQI+ activists **are particularly exposed to physical, digital and institutional violence**, several FIERCE Actions have developed strategies for self-defence and collective care. These initiatives are part of a **critical reflection on the sustainability of activism**, highlighting the need to protect activists while building spaces of support and resilience.

In the face of intensifying anti-feminist attacks, these projects have **strengthened the ability of activists to defend themselves, individually and collectively**, while incorporating an intersectional approach to violence. In this way, they are breaking new ground by **making care a tool of political resistance**, deconstructing the idea that struggle and exhaustion are inseparable.

Feminist and queer self-defence

- *The Italian National Lab self-defence manual (coordinated by Smart Venice) (Italy)*: Developed in response to sexist violence and anti-gender attacks in schools, this manual offers **concrete tools for physical and psychological self-defence**, inspired by critical feminist pedagogies. Its approach is based on **intergenerational transmission of knowledge**, enabling new generations of activists to acquire protection and response strategies adapted to hostile contexts.
- As part of the Intersectional Bystander Workshop and Game at The Danish Youth Democracy Festival 2024, developed notably by the Danish National Lab, a card game and workshop were created to help young people (secondary school students) become active bystanders in the fight against discrimination and sexism. Drawing on testimonies of sexism experienced by minorities that were collected through the National Lab, this initiative not only educates participants about the realities of intersectional discrimination but also empowers them to take ownership of their actions. By fostering critical thinking and collective solidarity, it enables young people to challenge oppressive systems, transform their communities, reinforce their action capacity and emancipation, and make them allies in the struggle for gender equality.

Practices of care and mutual support among activists

Faced with the exhaustion associated with feminist struggles, several initiatives have set up spaces dedicated to **rest, discussion and collective care**. These facilities, inspired by feminist, afro-descendant and queer feminist practices, are based on an approach to resistance that incorporates **the body and emotion as political dimensions of the struggle**. As one participant put it: "**We have learnt that taking care of ourselves also means protecting our movement in the long term**".

These initiatives show that **democratic innovation lies not only in visible forms of mobilisation, but also in the ability of movements to protect and strengthen themselves and to sustain their struggles**

over the long term. They reaffirm that **taking care of activists also means preserving the vitality and effectiveness of intersectional feminist struggles.**

4. SUCCESS, CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

4.1.1. Successes

FIERCE Actions carriers, by responding to the post-action questionnaire (annex 2), highlighted the following elements as their most notable successes:

Strengthening Networks and Alliances – Many actions successfully created or reinforced feminist and LGBTQI+ networks, fostering collaboration across different groups and generations. For example, the feminist exhibition on reproductive rights developed by the FIERCE National Lab in Slovenia is declared to have helped unite activists and increase visibility for feminist issues. Similarly, the LGBTQI+ Radar created networking between organisations and people from various backgrounds. The project developed by the Greek National Lab (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) constructed a network of feminist organisations including organisations from secondary cities such as Karditsa, Volos and Rethymno. In Turkey, the project on LBTQIA+ Cartoons led to the formation of a working group for queer artists, which now meets regularly and has become a sustainable platform for solidarity and artistic expression.

Knowledge Production and Dissemination – Many groups developed practical resources, such as self-defense manuals, training guides, and digital platforms, to support activists, teachers, and feminist organizations. These tools were designed to be sustainable and widely accessible. The use of art, poetry, theater, and music allowed participants to challenge mainstream narratives and create alternative spaces for self-expression and activism. When it comes to the Bystander Workshop on Intersectional Sexism developed by the Danish National Lab and taking place at the Danish Youth Democracy Festival in 2024, it was originally planned as a one-time educational session, but the dialogue card game developed during the event was so well received that it is now used in several schools across Denmark. Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, which was one of the main contributors to this FIERCE Action, also regularly organized bystander workshops before this and has continued to do so after the festival. FIERCE research has shown how the domain of production of knowledge has been invested by anti-gender actors in Europe as a main tool for influencing public debate. It seems therefore essential that feminist actors continue to invest in knowledge production to maintain alternative discourses and debates. The platform on anti-gender movements developed by the French National Lab gathers and shares in one place resources developed by various organisations to allow their circulation. It also provides a version of the results of FIERCE in French in a format accessible to all within the feminist movements, beyond the academic audience. The documentation produced are also tools that support feminists and feminist movements nation-wide in their linguistic sphere of production. They are tools that reinforce the capacity of intervention of feminist organisations and ensures their strengthening in an increasingly adverse environment.

Tangible Benefits for Organizations – Many initiatives reported long-term gains, such as securing new funding opportunities, expanding their volunteer base, and improving internal capacities for future projects. When it comes to the Musafir project in Greece focused on Feminist and Migrant Storytelling, it aimed to create an archive of migrant and gendered experiences through storytelling and performance. However, beyond the product of the workshop it turns out that the participants became

deeply involved in shaping the project, forming a collective team now ready to continue working together on new initiatives.

Campaigns reached out to larger circles than expected. The campaign Orange Days in Aalborg (Denmark) declares that it successfully raised awareness on gender-based violence, with public happenings, panel debates, and workshops drawing in a larger and more engaged audience than expected. The distribution of goodies at all events ensured that knowledge and resources continued to circulate beyond the original campaign. The Feminist Exhibition on Reproductive Rights (Slovenia) was originally designed as a local awareness campaign, but it gained significant public and media attention, far exceeding expectations. The creation of an online version further extended its reach, making it accessible long after the project ended.

Overall, the FIERCE Actions claim to have successfully fostered intersectional, inclusive, and democratic innovation and laid the groundwork for continued activism and advocacy. These examples show that the FIERCE Actions were not only effective but also had long-term ripple effects, leading to new networks, publications, and ongoing activism beyond their initial scope. Feminist movements developed initiatives that go in the directions of the recommendations developed by the members of the FIERCE Transnational Network, including the willingness to strengthen the capacity of the feminist actors and to mobilise against anti-gender movements. These are self-managed, bottom-up initiatives that would largely benefit from being scaled-up and consolidated.

FIERCE Actions explored several new unexpected topics, revealing how ensuring the participation and co-construction by underrepresented groups leads to the opening of the public debate in unexpected directions.

- For instance, the Feminist Exhibition in Slovenia was initially planned to focus solely on **abortion rights**, but after preparatory discussion groups, it expanded to include **contraception, artificial insemination, and sex education**, as well as **institutional violence in reproductive healthcare**, leading to a dedicated discussion group where women shared experiences of medical discrimination.
- The so-called ‘Nordic paradox’ — where countries with strong gender equality policies still experience high rates of gender-based violence — emerged as a critical theme in Denmark. This highlighted systemic blind spots that prevent effective policy interventions.

4.1.2. Challenges faced by FIERCE Actions

The respondents highlighted several limits and challenges of the FIERCE Actions.

Many highlighted time and funding constraints. Many actions faced difficulties due to limited time for preparation, promotion, and execution and would have benefitted from longer implementation period. Several initiatives, including in Poland and Turkey, mentioned venue and logistical issues. This reveals limited capacity of the small-scale initiatives in adverse political contexts. Notably, sometimes finding suitable locations for events was a problem, especially in cities where cultural spaces were politically controlled. In some cases, events had to be moved at the last minute, such as the workshop in Gardeja, which was cancelled by the local mayor, even though she held pro-abortion views, due to fear of political repercussions. To mitigate these limitations, some initiatives were able to lever additional funds for the continuation of their process, such as *Tant que je serais noire* in France and continue the action initiated as a FIERCE Action beyond the limited timespan available in the project (November to March 2025), but

this comes as an exception. If such a project was replicated, and to go beyond the frame of pilot actions, it would be desirable to be able to dedicate more time and funds to such actions.

Some teams mention their lack of expertise in communication or specific technical skills in graphic design, sound engineering, and social media management, making it harder to promote events and create high-quality materials. This goes in the direction of FIERCE findings throughout Europe. Feminist organisations mostly rely on volunteering time, and although this creates spaces for experimentation, notably on new forms of governance, this also comes with capacity deficits. This highlights that in order to strengthen the feminist input into our democracies, it is essential to invest in supporting financially and operationally those extremely innovative and flexible movements, which often lack some capacities. One proposal of FIERCE is also to ensure the pooling and the sharing of resources in Europe via operating transnational networks, which can work at the strengthening of feminist initiatives locally.

Safety and backlash were also mentioned as strong limitations: Ensuring the safety of participants was a concern, especially for events addressing gender-based violence and LGBTQ+ rights. Some workshops faced anti-feminist or reactionary opposition, making it difficult to maintain a safe and inclusive environment. Some initiatives faced censorship on platforms like Instagram, particularly when sharing information about abortion and reproductive rights. Other forms of opposition also appeared that challenged the implementation of intersectional practice. For instance, in Turkey, some left-wing trade unions and activist groups reacted negatively to the work proposed by feminist movements, which was unexpected since they were assumed to be allies. This raised new questions about how feminist and labour movements intersect.

4.1.3. How to Improve? Innovation: a learning process

The respondents identified several elements of what they would do differently if they were to develop the FIERCE Actions again:

Although community involvement and diversity were a strength of many FIERCE actions, many of the respondents would have liked to have the means to go even further, notably by even deeper collaboration with local grassroots organizations, including survivors of gender-based violence as co-creators of events, rather than just participants, to ensure that their lived experiences shape future initiatives. Some initiatives originally focused on LGBTI+ individuals but later decided to expand participation to a broader audience to encourage solidarity and awareness across different social groups.

Finally, some teams realized they overestimated their capacity, leading to overwork. Future actions would involve better workload distribution and clear planning to avoid activist burnout. This is also a recurring issue mentioned by feminist movements within the FIERCE project and highlights the necessity to develop practices of care and of activism management practices among the feminist movement. This request has been notably addressed within FIERCE regarding the transnational feminist network.

4.1.4. Replicability

Several elements of democratic innovation developed by the FIERCE Actions are replicable and can be adapted to different contexts. Respondents highlighted key aspects that can be scaled or implemented elsewhere:

Open and Collaborative Frameworks: Maintaining horizontal, participatory decision-making ensures that all participants contribute meaningfully. This approach fosters ownership, inclusivity, and long-term

engagement. Many actions benefited from allowing volunteers to take ownership of organizing tasks, fostering a sense of community and commitment.

Building Intersectionality: This was done by grassroots and deliberate efforts to bring in under-represented groups and letting them the time and space to work on interconnections between their concerns and modes of action. By integrating feminist, queer, and anti-racist perspectives, they sought to ensure that all voices—especially those most marginalized—are part of democratic decision-making. Using theatre, music, and poetry to explore gendered and racialized oppression created engaging and transformative experiences.

Dialogue-Based Educational Tools: The dialogue card game used in the Danish Youth Democracy Festival was effective in engaging youth in discussions on intersectionality and sexism. Using games, representation, and visuals to trigger exchange with some categories of people, notably young people, appears as an effective way to engage and could be adapted for different issues and audiences.

Bridging Activist Work with Institutional Decision-Making: This can be done by building on community-led research. Grassroots knowledge production can nurture the exchange with policy makers.

Supporting Public Space Interventions: Many respondents found that organizing exhibitions, performances, and feminist street interventions was impactful in raising awareness. These methods can be easily replicated in other regions.

Investing the Digital Space: Using QR codes, online platforms, and multimedia content to spread feminist and LGBTQ+ knowledge worked well, especially in restrictive environments where in-person activism is risky.

5. CONCLUSION

This report analysed the FIERCE action, and more specifically the dimensions of democratic innovation within their conception and implementation.

The main outcomes of the analysis reveal that forms of innovation developed at a small grassroots level by feminist organisations have a specific potential when it comes to:

- bringing in new forms of governance
- implementing several dimensions of intersectionality
- involving under-represented groups
- integrating the dimensions of care
- recognizing non-academic, situated and experiential knowledge as a valid input in understanding
- dealing with democratic and public policy issues
- innovating forms of interactions with their audiences, using creative practices (theatre, games, music, food and other cultural actions) and campaigns (notably using a mix of online and offline tools).

The FIERCE Actions were able to put into practice some forms of intersectionality and to build new networks of actors.

However, these actions, when led by non-institutionalised groups of activists, often operating on a volunteer or quasi-volunteer basis, suffer limitations: due to time, finances, adverse political context and safety issues, as well as capacity issues.

In the short term, FIERCE Actions have provided – within dire constraints of time and finances - an impressive pool of outputs and knowledge in a large variety of languages that can be shared online and in the FIERCE Transnational network.

In the medium and long term, for European democracy and national democracies to benefit fully from the learnings and specific input from feminism, to increase the impact of such disperse, fluid, flexible and horizontal modes of action within the civic space, it is essential to help them strengthen: by building effective networks in which peer learning and capacity building can be shared and co-constructed, by bringing in long term financial support, and by supporting forms of community-based initiatives and knowledge production.

6. References

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7. ANNEXES: Questionnaires

Annex 1 – FIERCE Actions: Open Call Application Form

This annex presents the original application template used to collect essential information about each FIERCE Action, including background, objectives, methodology, and anticipated outcomes.

FIERCE Actions – Open Call Application

Organization Information

- **Organization Name:**
 - **Country:**
 - **Legal Status:**
 - **Contact Person and Role:**
 - **Address:**
 - **Email:**
 - **Telephone:**
 - **Website and Social Media:**
-

Background

- **Section: Description**
 - **Title:**
 - **Summary:**
 - **Objectives:**
 - **Section: Development**
 - **Details:**
 - **Implementation:**
 - **Target Audience:**
-

Eligibility

- **Democratic Innovation:**
 - **Feminist Approach:**
 - **Experience:**
-

Output

- **Milestones:**
 - **Outcomes:**
 - **Impact:**
-

Funding

- **Budget:**
 - **Total Amount Requested:**
-

Additional Information

- **Partnerships and Collaborations:**
 - **Replicability (potential to be adapted or reproduced elsewhere):**
-

Availability for FIERCE Project Activities

Please indicate your availability or agreement in principle for the following:

- I agree in principle to invite one FIERCE project partner to attend the Action, in part or whole, depending on the timeline.
 - I agree in principle for one representative of the Action to take part in 2 online discussions (between 30 and 45 minutes each) with FIERCE project partners.
 - I agree to write a simple narrative report at the end of the Action based on a template provided by the FIERCE project coordinators.
 - I agree in principle that one representative of the Action will be available to take part in the **FIERCE Winter Week**, from **4th to 7th November 2024**, in **Venice**.
 - **If you answered 'No' to the FIERCE Winter Week, please explain why:**
 - I agree in principle that one representative of the Action will be available to take part in the **Transnational Network**.
-

Declaration

Please sign or confirm your agreement with the above commitments and the information provided.

Annex 2 – Questionnaire on the Democratic Innovation of Your FIERCE Action

This annex contains a detailed questionnaire designed to assess the democratic innovation aspects of each FIERCE Action, focusing on implementation, feminist practices, participation, and impact.

Questionnaire on the Democratic Innovation of Your FIERCE Action

This report aims to inform FIERCE research and allow to learn from your FIERCE Action.

This report allows you to reflect and to share your reflections on the FIERCE Action's achievement and practices and on ways to improve and better reach your feminist objectives in the future in your context.

Please be as clear and open as possible when answering. Your answers will not be shared outside of the FIERCE researchers group. Your answers will allow us to compile an overall analysis of the FIERCE Actions and of the Democratic Innovation Processes assessed in your practices. We are very grateful that you share this information with us and are happy of the opportunity to learn from each other's practices.

Each question has several lead questions, which are teasers and triggers to guide your answers. Please provide an answer to each question main question but do not feel obliged to reply to every sub-question, should this not be relevant for your action.

We have previously carefully read your applications, thus we prompt you to bring new elements here that may be useful to get a better insight of the implementation of the action. No need to repeat what we already got from you when you applied.

Please note that what you write in the report will not impact on the payment of the second installment of the FIERCE Action's fund, as long as you have completed the action.

General Information

Organization			name *
Country *			
Legal			status
Contact	person	and	role
Address			
Email			
Telephone			
Website and social media			

Description of Your FIERCE Action

- **Please describe what you did ***
(*e.g., advocacy or communication campaign, workshop, roundtable, publication, cultural activities...*)
 - **What do you believe are the most important characteristics of your action?**
(*Approach, target group, activities, etc.*)
 - **Did the Action address challenges related to democracy, equality, or inclusion?**
(*Max 300 words*)
-

Set-Up and Implementation Process

Governance of Your Action *

- **Who composed the organizing group?**

- **Was there diversity in status, geography, background?**
- **Were different types of organizations involved?** (e.g. feminist groups, civil society, institutions)
(Max 300 words)

Participation & Decision-Making *

- **How were decisions made in the group** (consensus, negotiation, vote...)?
- **Were participants involved in development or implementation?**
(Max 500 words)

Intervention Logic and Approach *

- **What was the project's main approach?** (e.g., intersectional, bottom-up, community-based, popular education, etc.)
(Max 300 words)

Location of the Action *

- **Where was it organized?**
- **Did the location help reach underrepresented or hard-to-reach groups?**
(Max 300 words)

Relevance in Your Context *

- How was the action received locally/regionally/nationally?
- Did it deepen reflection or trigger feedback?
- What impact did it have on the root causes of the issue addressed?
(Max 400 words)

Analysis of Action and Results

- **Did the implementation differ from your original vision?**
(Max 400 words)
- **Were your main objectives met, exceeded, or underperformed?**
(Max 300 words)
- **Did unexpected issues/themes emerge?**
(Max 300 words)
- **If you were to do it again, what would you change?**
(Max 300 words)

Target Audience and Diversity *

- **Who were the target groups?**
- **How were participants selected?**

- **Was the group diverse** (race, gender, class, ability, locality)?
- **What was the quantitative and qualitative participation outcome?**
(Max 400 words)

Democratic Innovation Characteristics *

Check all that apply:

- Develops new governance mechanisms
- Creates platforms for mobilization
- Communication campaigns to combat anti-gender discourse
- Artistic/street/cultural activities to involve underrepresented groups
- Training courses
- Feminist assemblies or solution-driven encounters
- Other: *[Please specify]*

- **Describe other ways your Action represents a democratic innovation:**
(Max 500 words)
- **Did your feminist approach develop new practices?**
(Max 400 words)

Impact, Influence, Sustainability & Replicability

- **Did the Action reinvent underused spaces?**
(Max 300 words)
- **Did it foster new alliances (cross-sectoral or with minority groups)?**
(Max 200 words)
- **Did it lead to new data collection? ***
(Max 200 words)
- **Did it influence public policy? ***
(Max 300 words)
- **What difficulties did you encounter and how did you overcome them?**
(Max 300 words)
- **How might this Action influence your future practices or your partners'?**
(Max 200 words)
- **Were there concrete benefits for stakeholders or your organization? If yes, please explain.**
(Max 300 words)

+ Additional Information

Declaration *

I, the undersigned, declare that the information provided is accurate and complete to the best of my knowledge.

